
ASSIMILATION IS THE PROCESS OF CHANGING THE ADOPTED WORD

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Abstract.

The following article deals with words, which they migrate from one language into another adjust themselves to their new environment and get adapted to the norms of the recipient language. They undergo certain changes which gradually erase their foreign features, and, finally, they are assimilated. Sometimes the process of assimilation develops to the point when the foreign origin of a word is quite unrecognizable (dinner, cat, take, cup). Others, though well assimilated, still bear traces of their foreign background. Distance and development, for instance, are identified as borrowings by their French suffixes, skin and sky by the Scandinavian initial sk, police and regime by the French stress on the last syllable.

Keys words.

assimilation, word, suffixes, declension, narrowing, shifting, specialization, generalization.

The term assimilation of a loan word is used to denote a partial or total conformation to the phonetical, graphical and morphological standards of the receiving language and its semantic system, i.e. the process of assimilation of borrowings includes changes in sound form, morphological structure, grammar characteristics, meaning and usage.

Phonetic assimilation comprises changes in sound form and stress. Sounds that were alien to the English language were fitted into its scheme of sounds, e.g. In the recent French borrowings *communiqué*, *café* the long [e] and [c] are rendered with the help of [ei]. The accent is usually transferred to the first syllable in the words from foreign sources. The lasting nature of phonetic adaptation is best shown by comparing Norman French borrowings to later ones. The Norman borrowings have for a long time been fully adapted to the phonetic system of the English language: such words as *table*, *plate*, *courage*, *chivalry* bear no phonetic traces of their French origin. Some of the later (Parisian) borrowings, even the ones borrowed as early as the 15th c., still sound surprisingly French: *regime*, *valise*,

matinee, cafe, ballet. In these cases phonetic adaptation is not completed. The three stages of gradual phonetic assimilation of French borrowings can be illustrated by different phonetic variants of the word garage: (Amer.). The degree of phonetic adaptation depends on the period of borrowing: the earlier the period is the more completed is this adaptation.

Grammatical adaptation consists in a complete change of the former paradigm of the borrowed word (i. e. system of the grammatical forms peculiar to it as a part of speech). If it is a noun, it is certain to adopt, sooner or later, a new system of declension; if it is a verb, it will be conjugated according to the rules of the recipient language. Yet, this is also a lasting process. The Russian noun пальто was borrowed from French early in the 19th c. and has not yet acquired the Russian system of declension. The same can be said about such English Renaissance borrowings as datum (pl. data), phenomenon (pl. phenomena), criterion (pl. criteria) whereas earlier Latin borrowings such as cup, plum, street, wall were fully adapted to the grammatical system of the language long ago.

By semantic adaptation is meant adjustment to the system of meanings of the vocabulary. Borrowing is generally caused either by the necessity to fill a gap in the vocabulary or by a chance to add a synonym conveying an old concept in a new way. Yet, the process of borrowing is not always so purposeful, logical and efficient as it might seem at first sight. Sometimes a word may be borrowed "blindly", so to speak, for no obvious reason, to find that it is not wanted because there is no gap in the vocabulary nor in the group of synonyms which it could conveniently fill. Quite a number of such "accidental" borrowings are very soon rejected by the vocabulary and forgotten. But there are others which manage to take root by the process of semantic adaptation. The adjective large, for instance, was borrowed from French in the meaning of "wide". It was not actually wanted, because it fully coincided with the English adjective wide without adding any new shades or aspects to its meaning. This could have led to its rejection. Yet, large managed, to establish itself very firmly in the English vocabulary by semantic adjustment. It entered another synonymic group with the general meaning of "big in size". At first it was applied to objects characterised by vast horizontal dimensions, thus retaining a trace of its former meaning, and now, though still bearing some features of that meaning, is successfully competing with big having approached it very closely, both in frequency and meaning.

The adjective gay was borrowed from French in several meanings at once: "noble of birth", "bright, shining", "multi-coloured". Rather soon it shifted its

ground developing the meaning “joyful, high-spirited” in which sense it became a synonym of the native merry and in some time left it far behind in frequency and range of meaning. This change was again caused by the process of semantic adjustment: there was no place in the vocabulary for the former meanings of gay, but the group with the general meaning of “high spirits” obviously lacked certain shades which were successfully supplied by gay.

The adjective nice was a French borrowing meaning “silly” at first. The English change of meaning seems to have arisen with the use of the word in expressions like a nice distinction, meaning first “a silly, hair-splitting distinction”, then a precise one, ultimately an attractive one. But the original necessity for change was caused once more by the fact that the meaning of “foolish” was not wanted in the vocabulary and therefore nice was obliged to look for a gap in another semantic field.

Thus the process of semantic assimilation has many forms:

- 1) narrowing of meanings (usually polysemantic words are borrowed in one of the meanings);
- 2) specialization or generalization of meanings,
- 3) acquiring new meanings in the recipient language,
- 4) shifting a primary meaning to the position of a secondary meaning.

The degree of assimilation depends upon the length of period during which the word has been used in the receiving language, upon its importance for communication purpose and its frequency. Oral borrowings due to personal contacts are assimilated more completely and more rapidly than literary borrowings, i.e. borrowings through written speech.

Loan words according to the degree of assimilation fall into three groups:

- a) completely assimilated loan words,
- b) partially assimilated loan words,
- c) unassimilated loan words or barbarisms.

The group of partially assimilated words may be subdivided depending on the aspect that remains unaltered, i.e. according to whether the word retains features of spelling, pronunciation, morphology or denotation (when the word denotes some specific realia) that are not English. The third group is not universally accepted, as it may be argued that words not changed at all cannot form part of the English vocabulary, because they occur in speech only, but do not enter the language.

Completely assimilated loan words are found in all the layers of older borrowings. They may belong to the first layer of Latin borrowings, e. g. cheese, street, wall or wine. Among Scandinavian loan words we find such frequent nouns as husband, fellow, gate, root, wing; such verbs as call, die, take, want and adjectives like happy, ill, low, odd and wrong. Completely assimilated French words are extremely numerous and frequent: table, chair, face, figure, finish, matter etc. A considerable number of Latin words borrowed during the revival of learning are at present almost indistinguishable from the rest of the vocabulary (Eng. animal, article, Ukr. кума, праця, хлопець, казан, хліб, хворий, хватати).

The number of completely assimilated loan words is many times greater than the number of partially assimilated ones. They follow all morphological, phonetical and orthographic standards. Being very frequent and stylistically neutral, they may occur as dominant words in synonymic groups. They take an active part in word-formation. Moreover, their morphological structure and motivation remain transparent, so that they are morphologically analysable and therefore supply the English vocabulary not only with free forms but also with bound forms, as affixes are easily perceived and separated in series of loan words that contain them. Such are, for instance, the French suffixes -age, -ance and -mentr and the English modification of French -esse and -fier, which provide speech material to produce hybrids like shortage, goddess, hindrance, speechify, and endearment. The free forms, on the other hand, are readily combined with native affixes, e. g. pained, painful, painfully, painless, painlessness, all formed from pain<Fr. peine<Lat. poena >Gr. poine. "penalty".

Conclusion

Completely assimilated loan words are also indistinguishable phonetically. A loan word never brings into the receiving language the whole of its semantic structure if it is polysemantic in the original language. And even the borrowed variants are for the most part changed and specialized in the new system. The word sport can serve as an illustration. It had a much wider scope in Old French denoting pleasures, making merry and entertainments in general. It was borrowed into Middle English in this character but gradually acquired the additional meaning of outdoor games and exercise, and in this new meaning was borrowed into many European languages and became international. It is convenient to classify and study loan words as oppositions of the words as they exist in the receiving language with their prototypes in the source language, on the one hand,

and with words of the same lexico-grammatical class or (depending on the level chosen) of the same morphological or phonetic pattern in the receiving language.

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